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Translation Problems of International Words

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Annotation: *In this article, the topics of common problems in translation studies, as well as the current demand for translation studies and its role in society, are discussed.*

Keywords: *text, translation, lexicon, term, translation problems, transformation (change), information.*

Introduction. Today, the rapid development of modern globalization and intercultural relations, the expansion of international relations, the development of trade-economic and financial relations between countries, the strengthening of the process of integration of European countries and the whole world, the development of science and technology, the continuous flow of scientific and technical information Nowadays, the importance of foreign languages as effective factors of organic exchange deserves great attention. Also, at the stage of economic, scientific, technical and cultural development, a foreign language is widely used as a means of oral and written communication between representatives of different peoples of the world.

Due to the rapid development of knowledge and technologies, translators who have practical skills in translating scientific and technical texts related to various fields, covering all aspects in today's society and in the era of changing conditions of the modern economy

➤ Specialists are in special demand today. Therefore, the need for highly educated translators is increasing day by day.

Due to the development of modern technologies, today, scientists from different countries of the world have the opportunity to quickly exchange information and conduct joint research, and thanks to these means of communication, unprecedented results are being achieved in modern science. In such conditions, the need for high-quality translation of scientific literature is significantly increasing in many manufacturing organizations. And translators must constantly add translations of scientific literature to their vocabulary, increase their ability to understand terms and know their meaning.

Therefore, when translating scientific and technical terms, the translator should first of all pay great attention to the meaning from the existing scientific and technical point of view, and then it is necessary to have the ability to compare with narrow scientific and technical terms.

Literature review. In the process of translation of scientific and technical texts, the following requirements should be followed: translation equivalence, translation accuracy, quality of translation data, logic of translation and quality of its coverage. In order to have a quality translation of a scientific and technical text, the translator must have the following knowledge and skills:

- Must have knowledge of foreign language theory, phonetics, lexis and grammatical structure of the language;
- Translation of scientific and technical texts to the practice of the skills;
- Linguistic practical knowledge (translation methods, transformation, the ability to replace the equivalent of words, the ability to add words, the ability to describe with terms, etc.);
- In the process of translating the text, it is necessary to have extralinguistic knowledge and the ability to use the content of sentences and sentences, in which it was required to have sufficient information in the translation of a special scientific-technical text.

Research methodology. One of the main unknown problems in translation is that the translator does not have a complete understanding of what "scientific translation" is. In order to successfully perform scientific translation, the translator must have an idea of how it differs from other types of translation. In general, the translation of the scientific method includes many texts related to the research topic - from theses, includes abstracts and article reviews, diplomas, dissertations and monograph manuscripts.

When translating the above types of work, attention should be paid to the following factors: the purpose of translation, the method of translation, the organization of the text in the translation and the relationship between its parts.

In addition to the external structure of academic texts (chapters, sections, paragraphs), there is also an internal structure. The translation of scientific texts has its own characteristics - it is a method of defining material problems from general information and presenting their solution. For example, English has a number of words and phrases that are used for different purposes, to connect pieces of text together, as well as to move from one phrase to another.

Grammatical problems in translation.

The style of scientific communication has its own grammatical features. For example, when some texts are translated from English to Uzbek, in some cases lexical meaning is lost and verbs acquire abstract meaning.

In these cases, we can see that the semantic load falls on verbs instead of noun phrases. In other words, verbs perform an important grammatical function in these sentences.

Discussion and result. In general, a scientific text must have a clear statement of logic, and providing a correct and high-quality translation of this logic is one of the most important tasks of a translator. Texts in the scientific style, in most cases, have a homogeneous appearance, but these texts have expressive features. In such texts, interrogative sentences are rarely used, even if they are used, they are directed to draw the attention of the reader who is familiar with the text. One of the characteristics of scientific texts is that they do not use emotional expressions.

The general theory of translation systematizes the conclusions derived from the concrete experience of translation and creates a basis for it. In the process of translation, of translation its results and ideas are summarized, and the conditions and factors specific to translation are taken into account in the translation activity.

Conclusion. A special theory of translation (or research on translation focused on a pair in linguistics) should take into account the equivalents, variants of the correspondence between two languages, as well as the factors and criteria for their selection in a specific situation. The main method of studying translation phenomena within this theory is the comparison of two languages. For example: Uzbek and Russian, or Russian and English, or English and German.

The transformational theory (model) of translation is represented by making changes to the translated text during the translation activity. The reason is that in some cases the meaning of the text cannot be fully translated or it is difficult to translate.

References

1. Ogli, Kuvonov Zarifjon Maxsiddin. "Die vorteile und nachteile der online-bildung." Academic research in educational sciences 2.CSPI conference (2021): 478-481.
2. Зариф, Кувонов (2020). Немис тилига франсуз тилидан узлашган сузларнинг структурал-семантик таджики, XXI аср тилшунослиги ва таржимашунослигининг долзарб муаммолари: назария, амалиёт, инновация
3. Кувонов, Зарифжон (2020). Немис тилига узлашган сузларнинг келиб чикдш тарихи. Проблемы и перспективы развития современной науки в странах Европы и Азии - XXIV Международной научно-практической интернет-конференции.
4. Ерова С. Н. История заимствований слов в русском языке Ученые записки Худжандского государственного университета им. академика Б. Гафурова. Гуманитарные науки. – 2017. – № 2 (51). – С. 155. Там же. – С. 155–156. 4. Лесников С. В. «Основные латинские терминологические элементы и термины метаязыка лингвистики» Сыктывкарский государственный университет «Научные ведомости» Серия Гуманитарные науки. 2011. №12 (107). Выпуск 10
5. Ожегов С.И., Н. Ю. Шведовой « Толковый словарь русского языка» - М.,2010г 6. Lashkova G. V., Matyashevskaya A. I. Anglicizmy v sovremennom russkom yazyke. [Anglicisms in modern Russian]. In: Izvestiya of Saratov University. Philology. Journalism. [Izvestiya Saratovskogo universiteta. Novaya seriya. Seriya: Filologiya. Zhurnalistika]. 2022. Vol. 22. Iss. 2.